

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERNAL CONTROL AND INTERNAL AUDIT
AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE BUSINESS PERFORMANCE
OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES**

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The Effectiveness of Internal Control and Internal Audit and Their Influence on the Business Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises

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Abstract

This quantitative study determined the level of effectiveness of internal control and internal audit as well as its relationship to business performance and examined their influence on Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). It employed a quantitative-descriptive and cross-sectional research design. The respondents of the study were the accountants or the employees of 21 SMEs within the vicinity of General Santos City, Philippines. The respondents must be employed by the businesses that they work with and have performed at least one internal audit within the entity and must have knowledge in internal controls as well as internal audit. Random sampling and adapted-modified research survey questionnaires were used to identify the respondent's level of effectiveness of internal control and internal audit and their influence to the business performance of the SMEs. The data gathered were treated using mean, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, and multiple regression. Moreover, the results of the study showed that the level of effectiveness of internal control and internal audit and the business performance of the SMEs were considered high with the overall mean of 4.19, 4.32, and 3.97, respectively. Hence, it is recommended to use this study as a basis to identify any potential issues to enhance and strengthen the level of effectiveness of internal control and internal audit and their influence on the SMEs' business performance.

Keywords: *internal control, internal audit, business performance, quantitative research*

Introduction

In the realm of small businesses, struggling with limited resources, certain systems not only address issues but also facilitate business enhancement and adaptation to change. The strength of internal control and audit within Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) exhibits considerable variability, with some maintaining robust systems tailored to their needs while others face limitations due to resource constraints. This variability extends to the internal audit function, ranging from entities with periodic assessments to those lacking dedicated capacities. The small and medium enterprise sector holds immense significance in the Philippine economy, representing a majority of businesses and contributing two-thirds of total employment, despite comparatively lower productivity levels (Canare & Francisco, 2020).

Internal control shortcomings can expose a company to operational and financial losses if they are not addressed. Some of the problems that the business might encounter are separation of duties, corporate governance, lack of training, and lack of adequate resources. A higher risk of mistakes or fraud can emerge from an ineffective use of internal control and internal audit on the business performance. It can cause the business performance itself to falter. Understanding the influence of internal control and audit on SMEs carries implications for operational efficiency, risk management, and financial health. This insight paves the way for tailored solutions, enabling SMEs to strengthen internal structures, mitigate risks, and improve overall performance. Stakeholders, from investors to policymakers, benefit from this knowledge in fostering a conducive environment for SME growth.

Recent research by Ghani et al. (2021), report from the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE) emphasized that businesses with strong internal controls and proactive internal audits are less vulnerable to financial losses from fraud, highlighting the critical role of internal audit in fraud prevention and maintaining a solid control system. Controls serve as an assurance that risks are at acceptable levels and do not jeopardize an organization's objectives. Controls must be effectively defined by identifying and assessing potential risks, mapping their causes and consequences, and establishing and implementing appropriate controls to reduce those risks. Organizational goals should be clearly stated to ensure that controls are adequate for the specific risks that could have a different impact on the firm. Once this is accomplished, controls to mitigate the causes of the identified risks can be implemented (Borsalli, 2022).

According to Li et al. (2018), during the period of economic transition, in order to protect stakeholders' lawful rights and interests, the beneficial role of internal control in corporate governance should be strengthened. The study shows that effective internal control has greatly encouraged businesses to take on social duties and has resulted in fair and long-term benefits for stakeholders. Additionally, strong internal controls dramatically raise the bar for corporate social responsibility fulfillment and eliminates further risk of social responsibility. A technique that can be used to increase internal control's effectiveness is the use of an Accounting Information System (AIS). According to one study, companies can support operations with IT systems thanks to the advancement and application of information technology (IT), which improves operating performance. However, in order to exercise effective control, companies must adapt their internal control techniques and methods to computerization (AIS), as the adoption of high-quality internal controls has an impact on operations and the achievement of operations.

Moreover, a recent study by Turetken et al. (2020) conducted a systematic review of the literature to find pertinent articles and collect

and synthesize data on the factors that affect the efficacy of the internal audit function. They divide the variables that affect the internal audit function's efficacy into supply and demand categories. The elements connected to internal auditors' self-evaluation fall under the supply category, whilst the audit committee and other stakeholders' perceptions fall under the demand category. The effectiveness of internal audit should be evaluated in light of its contribution to the effective and efficient provision of services.

According to Hassan et al. (2019), senior management support, a lack of internal auditor competency, and scarce resources all have a beneficial impact on the performance of internal auditors in Jordan. On the other hand, the authors discovered that work complexity had a detrimental influence on the efficiency of internal auditors in the Jordanian public sector. Notably, comprehending the extrinsic elements that contribute to internal auditors' efficiency in Jordan's public sector might provide insights into many other comparable nations, particularly the Arab nations. The Jordanian government has been encouraged by related research to concentrate on the IAF and its effectiveness in order to lessen the issue of corruption in the public sector. Along with effectively distributing internal resources within public organizations through an internal audit, this should be done (Nawaiseh et al., 2021).

The study advises SMEs to establish an independent auditing department, which would not only contribute to value creation but also safeguard business growth by enhancing effective risk management and establishing a robust internal control (Nwinyokpugi & Ezeukwu, 2022). The results align with a similar study carried out in Ghana. The study's findings surprisingly indicated that internal audits tended to have adverse effects on the performance of listed enterprises. These results contradicted the commonly held belief that the oversight roles performed by internal auditors, focusing on auditing, financial reporting, internal control, and risk management within organizations, would inevitably lead to enhanced performance, safeguarding the interests of shareholders and the public (Puni & Anlesinya, 2019). Numerous studies have examined numerous elements in order to determine why IAF is ineffective (Conteh, 2021). For instance, Suleiman et al. (2021) discovered that a number of issues, such as limited resources, insufficiently experienced internal auditors, understaffed departments, and inadequate support from upper management, had a detrimental impact on the effectiveness of internal audit. Relevantly, (Musah, 2018) noticed a lack of support from upper management and competency as the causes of IAE insufficiency, which resulted in a variety of issues in businesses.

Although there are several studies conducted on the internal control and internal audit, there are limited studies that focus on the relation between internal audit as well as internal control on business performance and also there is no published studies related in the topics in General Santos City. This study will help fill this gap through determining the effectiveness of internal control and internal audit, and evaluating their influence on the Small and Medium Enterprises business performance. Moreover, this study utilized quantitative-descriptive analysis and cross-sectional approach to determining the effectiveness of internal control and internal audit and their influence on the business performance of SMEs.

Methodology

The study employed a quantitative-descriptive analysis coupled with a cross-sectional approach, chosen for their suitability in statistically examining the effectiveness of internal control and internal audit and their correlation with the business performance of SMEs (Tjombe, 2023). It involves 21 respondents who were randomly selected within the vicinity of General Santos City to answer the validated adapted-modified research survey questionnaire. The data was obtained with various statistical procedures through weighted mean and Pearson's Correlation Coefficient or Pearson R. Multiple Regression was utilized to determine the significant influence of internal control and internal audit of SMEs' business performance.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control

The result shows the level of effectiveness of internal control. This section is divided into five (5) sub-variables that showcase the performance of business according to the general controls, cash controls, operating expenditures, personnel, expenditures and travel, and information technology.

Table 1.1. *The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of General Controls*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
The department performs a monthly reconciliation/ review of its payroll reports.	4.19	Often
Spending appears to be within budget for the periods tested.	4.38	Often
The department has created, maintained, and made available to its faculty/staff a departmental policy and procedures manual.	4.38	Often
All year-end close procedures and/or deadlines are followed, as indicated by the appropriate personnel.	4.43	Often
Risk or obstacles to achieving those objectives have been identified.	4.00	Often
The overall effectiveness of the internal control system is routinely evaluated.	4.10	Often
Overall Mean	4.25	Often

Table 1.2. *The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of Cash Controls*

Items	Mean	Description
The department's petty cash funds are necessary and have procedures for control and reconciliation.	4.48	Often
The department does not have unauthorized bank accounts or change accounts.	4.00	Often
Cash deposits are sufficiently documented.	4.24	Often
The department's revenue-producing activities have established accounting procedures for compliance with BIR and Tax regulations.	4.67	Always
Employees responsible for cash handling and deposit preparation are familiar with applicable policies.	4.52	Always
Deposits are made promptly, that is, in the form of the following day.	4.00	Often
Daily collections are held securely until deposited. (i.e., kept in a fireproof result)	4.33	Often
Overall Mean	4.32	Often

Table 1.3. *The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of Operating Expenditures*

Items	Mean	Description
1. Check requests, including personal reimbursements, are properly authorized, sufficiently documented, and for appropriate purposes.	4.29	Often
2. Purchase acquisitions are properly authorized, sufficiently documented, and for appropriate purposes.	4.43	Often
3. Procurement card use, if applicable, is adequately controlled and transactions are properly reviewed and sufficiently documented, for appropriate organization purposes, and accounted for correctly in the financial system. Documents are retained per policy.	3.67	Often
4. Journal vouchers are appropriate, properly authorized, and adequately documented.	4.29	Often
Overall Mean	4.17	Often

Table 1.4. *The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of Personnel, Expenditures and Travel*

Items	Mean	Description
1. Timesheets are properly authorized and agree with payroll records.	4.38	Often
2. The organization tracks and maintains adequate records of employees' vacation leave and sick leave.	4.19	Often
3. Monthly telephone statements including cellular phone bills are reviewed for accuracy and personal calls.	3.38	Sometimes
4. Staff understands the organization's policy on personnel telephone calls.	3.95	Often
5. Travel/business expense reports are properly authorized and documented. Expenses comply with policy.	4.33	Often
6. Personnel do not make personal purchases through the organization's accounts.	3.86	Often
7. Department personnel are aware of the policy on conflicts of interest and have filed disclosure forms if appropriate.	4.33	Often
8. Staff morale is positive, employees seem competent, and the allocation of duties within the department promotes the efficient use of resources.	4.48	Often
9. Job descriptions are accurate and up-to-date. Major expectations are included in the job description.	4.24	Often
10. Staff payroll changes are documented.	4.38	Often
Overall Mean	4.15	Often

Table 1.5. *The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of Information Technology*

Items	Mean	Description
1. All department personnel familiar with the Organization Information Technology Responsible Use Policy.	3.90	Often
2. All department workstations upgraded with the latest security patches and virus protection	3.67	Often
3. The critical information backed-up and stored off-site.	3.81	Often
4. The sensitive information was protected by operator ID/password.	4.33	Often
5. All passwords are adequately controlled and protected from unauthorized use.	4.14	Often
6. The passwords kept confidential (i.e., not shared or posted at work sites)	4.67	Always
7. I am aware of any "default" passwords that are still being used for any IT applications rather than having been changed to more secure, personal passwords.	4.29	Often
8. The computer applications logged-off when the user is going to be away from the terminal or PC for an hour or more.	4.14	Often
9. The computers and servers are maintained in a secure area.	4.10	Often
10. The laptop computers are secured when not in use.	4.43	Often
11. Each of departmental server was equipped with an Uninterrupted Power Supply (UPS).	4.19	Often
12. Each department has a critical information system that was connected to an outside network that was protected by a firewall.	3.90	Often
Overall Mean	4.13	Often
Grand Mean	4.19	Often

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Audit

The succeeding results present the level of effectiveness of internal audit under two (2) variables: general expectations from internal audit and assessment of internal audit work.

Table 2.1. *The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Audit in terms of General Expectations from Internal Audit*

Items	Mean	Description
1. I consider that internal audit delivers added value to the department.	4.43	Often
2. I believe that internal audits improve the activity of the department.	4.43	Often
3. I consider that internal audit helps me in assuring the premises for the next projects.	4.71	Always
4. I have a general opinion regarding the internal audit's effectiveness for the whole organization.	4.14	Often
Overall Mean	4.43	Often

Table 2.2. *The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Audit in terms of Assessment of Internal Audit Work*

Items	Mean	Description
1. I consider that established objectives at the beginning of the audit mission were accomplished.	4.24	Often
2. I consider that communication between internal audit and external audit was efficient.	4.00	Often
3. I consider that audit work was efficiently performed according to the planning period.	4.00	Often
4. I consider that internal audit work was realized with responsibility.	4.48	Often
5. I consider that the findings are correctly argued and justified.	4.24	Often
6. I consider that internal audit recommendations are significant.	4.43	Often
7. I consider that the internal audit report was issued in a useful time.	4.33	Often
8. I consider that internal audit is clear and logical.	4.62	Always
Overall Mean	4.29	Often
Grand Mean	4.34	Often

The Level of Business Performance of the SMEs

The level of business performance of the SMEs is shown in the following results under two (2) variables: financial performance and non-financial performance.

Table 3.1. *The Level of Business Performance of the SMEs in terms of Financial Performance*

Items	Mean	Description
1. The profit of the company increased annually.	4.10	Often
2. The number of the company's assets increased.	3.86	Often
3. The number of working capitals increased.	3.76	Often
4. The number of sales growths increased.	3.67	Often
5. The number of cash flows increased monthly.	3.76	Often
Overall Mean	3.83	Often

Table 3.2. *The Level of Business Performance of the SMEs in terms of Non-Financial Performance*

Items	Mean	Description
1. Relations with suppliers are quite good and stable.	4.24	Often
2. We strongly involve our suppliers in our research and development processes.	4.10	Often
3. There are no cases in our company of people leaving for internal reasons.	4.05	Often
4. Productivity of employees is much higher than industry average.	4.05	Often
5. Employees' trust in leadership is high.	4.29	Often
6. Work organization is efficient.	3.76	Often
7. Employees feel very committed to the organization.	4.19	Often
8. The number of customer complaints within the last 12 months has decreased.	3.52	Often
9. We deal with customer complaints faster than our competitors.	4.10	Often
10. Risk-taking within the company is better than its competitors.	4.14	Often
Overall Mean	4.04	Often
Grand Mean	3.97	Often

Table 4. *Significant Relationship Between the Level of Internal Control and the Level of Business Performance of SMEs*

Variable	Level of Business Performance of the SMEs		Remarks
	r- value	p- value	
Internal Control	.625	.002	Significant

Table 5. *Significant Relationship Between the Level of Internal Audit and the Level of Business Performance of the SMEs*

Variable	Level of Business Performance of the SMEs		Remarks
	r- value	p- value	
Internal Audit	.355	.114	Not significant

Table 6. Internal Control and Internal Audit have a Significant Influence on the Business Performance of the SMEs

Independent variable	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error Beta		
(Constant)	.400	1.139	.351	.729
Control	.761	.269	.590	.011
Audit	.088	.252	.073	.731

Multiple R: 0.628
R-squared: 0.395
F-value: 5.872

Sig /P value: 0.011

Conclusions

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of General Controls

Table 1.1 illustrates the effectiveness of internal controls within businesses, particularly focusing on general controls. Among SMEs, following year-end closing guidelines and deadlines receives the highest rating with a mean score of 4.43. Additionally, SMEs are doing well in managing their spending, staying under budget during testing periods, and maintaining an updated policy and procedures handbook, both with a mean of 4.38. However, identifying risks or challenges to reaching goals got a lower mean of 4.00, still considered high. The data indicates an overall average of 4.25, which is interpreted high. This suggests that general controls are quite effective for internal control.

The data indicates an overall average of 4.25, which is interpreted high. This data highlights the significance SMEs place on maintaining strong internal controls, particularly in general controls. It underscores the importance of accuracy, regulatory compliance, and reliability in financial reporting. While the study reveals a commendable commitment to these controls, it also points out the need for proactive risk management to address potential challenges. There is room for improvement in assessing general controls, suggesting an opportunity for businesses to enhance their internal control practices.

The results diverge from those of a comparable study conducted in Mexico. The study reveals that micro and small businesses in Region XII State of Mexico face challenges in establishing an adequate general control system primarily due to the perceived high costs associated with implementation, which they are reluctant to bear. Additionally, a lack of economic resources further impedes their capacity to establish robust general controls. The managers and owners of these businesses demonstrate a lack of awareness regarding these control practices and its comprehensive requirements (Carbajal et al., 2021).

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of Cash Controls

In Table 1.2, SMEs demonstrate strong adherence to specific rules regarding record-keeping, government tax laws, and the BIR, scoring the highest mean of 4.67, interpreted as very high. Following closely is the practice of leveraging employees' knowledge about cash handling in operations, with a mean of 4.52, also interpreted as very high. Furthermore, maintaining consistency in financial activities, such as not changing accounts and timely handling of money, secures a lower mean of 4.00, still considered high. Moreover, addresses the effectiveness of internal control, specifically focusing on Cash Controls. Lastly the data reveals an overall mean of 4.32, signaling a high level of effectiveness in managing internal controls related to cash.

The data reveals an overall mean of 4.32 and is interpreted as high. This data suggests that well-defined procedures in income-generating activities contribute to better cash control. This implies that well-maintained and regularly reconciled in handling cash is essential for internal control to be effective. Moreover, well-maintained cash handling is essential for effective internal control, emphasizing the critical role of strong financial governance in preserving a business's financial stability.

In India, a comparable study indicated that, out of 53 respondents, there is a high adoption rate of cash controls. The study suggests that a significant number of respondents record transactions in personal notes, lacking a formal approach. Additionally, it was observed that these transactions are monitored on a daily basis. To enhance the development of a well-organized business, it is imperative to enhance the small business and its associated sector. Small business owners must possess both practical and theoretical knowledge of cash management for the effective operation of their businesses (Chakraborty & Singh, 2022).

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of Operating Expenditures

Table 1.3 discusses the effectiveness of internal control concerning operating expenditures. SMEs excel in ensuring that purchase acquisitions are appropriately authorized, well-recorded, and used for their intended purposes, garnering the highest mean of 4.43. Similarly, the vigilant checking of requests, including personal reimbursements, and the proper validation of journal vouchers obtained the second highest mean of 4.29. However, the utilization of procurement cards, obtained a lower mean of 3.67, suggesting that there is room for improvement in controlling procurement card use. Overall, the data reflects an average mean of 4.17, interpreted as high, suggesting highly effective management of operating expenditures for internal control.

This emphasizes the significance of having operating expenditures duly authorized, well-recorded, and purposefully utilized for effective business performance. Operating expenditures play a vital role in the daily functioning and revenue generation of a business.

It is imperative for companies to meticulously manage these expenses, ensuring alignment with intended purposes and contributing to overall profitability. The identified need for tighter controls in the use of procurement cards points towards an area for improvement, highlighting the potential to enhance the efficiency of internal controls in managing operating expenditures.

The results match another study done in a similar Indonesian business environment. In Primagama, the main business discussed, they've set up a good system to control how they spend money on day-to-day operations. Every spending needs the owner's clear approval, and then the branch manager double-checks it carefully. They have organized their money coming in and going out separately, and each party does its job following specific rules (Listya et al., 2022). Managing expenses safeguards financial stability, ensures long-term sustainability, and fosters growth in businesses.

According to Beaver (2020), operating expenditures serve as the lifeblood that sustains the day-to-day operations of any enterprise. Should these expenses exceed the total revenue amassed, the company will find itself unable to turn a profit. Therefore, it becomes imperative for businesses to meticulously analyze and manage these operating costs, striving to identify avenues for cost reduction and strategies that will bolster overall profitability. Tuovila (2021) notes that these expenses typically cover travel elements like air travel, lodging, dining, and ground transportation.

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of Personnel, Expenditures and Travel

Table 1.4 discusses the level of effectiveness of internal control in terms of Personnel, Expenditures and Travel. Results evaluate the effectiveness of internal control concerning personnel, expenditures, and travel. SMEs excel in fostering positive staff morale, deploying competent individuals, and efficiently distributing tasks, obtaining the highest mean of 4.48. Similarly, organizational performance demonstrates strong control, with the second highest mean of 4.38, ensuring that timesheets are appropriately authorized and align with payroll records, and staff payroll changes are well-documented. However, a lower mean of 3.38 highlights a need for better oversight of SME expenses, including cell phone bills, telephone statements, and personal calls. The data reveals an overall mean of 4.15 which is interpreted as high.

The data reveals an overall mean of 4.15 which is interpreted as high. Managing people, expenses, and travel is crucial for organizational effectiveness. Leave tracking and travel policy show promise, but controlling certain expenses and calls could use improvement. Improving these areas enhances operational efficiency and financial management in the organization.

A study on Chinese SMEs revealed consistent findings, highlighting their establishment of effective internal control systems. These businesses emphasize the protection of crucial information and the prevention of salary-related fraud. Detailed attendance records ensure compliance, boosting operational efficiency and overall business effectiveness (Wang et al., 2019).

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Control in terms of Information Technology

Table 1.5 discusses the level of effectiveness of internal control in terms of Information Technology. The highest mean, at 4.67 and interpreted as very high, pertains to SMEs' performance in safeguarding confidential passwords. Performance of SMEs laptop computers secured when not in use has obtained a second highest mean of 4.43 and is interpreted as high. Securing SMEs' laptop computers when not in use follows closely with the second-highest mean of 4.43, also interpreted as high. Meanwhile, the upgrade of SMEs' workstations with the latest security patches and virus protection obtained the lowest mean of 3.67, still interpreted as high. Lastly the table resulted in an overall mean of 4.13, interpreted as high, indicating a high level of efficacy in the organization's internal control regarding information technology.

The data suggests that strong emphasis on password security and the positive performance in IT internal control are crucial to perform a commendable level of efficacy in the organization's internal control regarding information technology. This indicates that SMEs are generally performing well in managing and securing their IT infrastructure, which is crucial for protecting sensitive data and maintaining business continuity. Overall, there's a solid foundation in place, but ongoing efforts are necessary to stay ahead of potential threats.

According to Akmesse and Ilgaz (2021), a study in Turkey asked different businesses about using computer systems well to control things inside the company. It showed that keeping computer systems up-to-date and having good rules for controlling things inside the company are very important. They say that having good control over these computer systems can help keep track of how well the company is doing with its day-to-day money coming in.

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Audit in terms of General Expectations from Internal Audit

In Table 2.1, SMEs' internal audit helps in assuring the premises for the next projects has obtained a highest mean of 4.71 which is interpreted as very high. The organization utilized internal audit to deliver added value to the department and improve the activity of the organization, both got the second highest mean of 4.43 which was interpreted as high. The business performance of SME employees has an overall assessment of the executions of internal audits across the entire organization with the lowest mean of 4.14 and is interpreted as high. The data shows an overall mean of 4.43 and is interpreted as high which indicates that the internal audit is effective and beneficial to the organization.

SME employees widely recognize the significant contributions made by internal audits, acknowledging their substantial impact in

elevating departmental activities and overall organizational effectiveness. Respondents consistently emphasize the important role of internal audits in paving the way for future projects, consistently appraising its high effectiveness. This collective viewpoint underscores the profound value attributed to internal audits, affirming its pivotal role as a driving force behind the success of various departments. Such acclaim serves as a testament to the positive and influential role internal audits play within the organization, affirming its stature as a key contributor to departmental and organizational success.

The results aligned with a study conducted in South Africa. Internal auditors interviewed emphasized the significance of internal audit and its role in ensuring quality assurance. Respondents highlighted satisfaction with the internal audit function (IAF), its perceived value addition, and its utilization by external auditors as critical aspects. These factors hold importance as internal auditors are expected to provide the consulting anticipated by stakeholders (Erasmus & Coetzee, 2018).

The Level of Effectiveness of Internal Audit in terms of Assessment of Internal Audit Work

As shown in Table 2.2, SMEs' execution of internal audit is clear and logical and has obtained the highest mean of 4.62 which is interpreted as very high. The second highest mean obtained 4.43 and is interpreted as high, states that the organization's internal audit recommendations are significant. The SMEs' performance utilized communication between internal audit as well as external audit was efficient and audit work was realized with responsibility obtained the lowest mean of 4.00 and are interpreted as high. The data obtained an overall mean of 4.29 and is interpreted as high, designating the efficiency and effectiveness of the internal audit process. The grand mean for this section is 4.34 which is interpreted as high, indicating that respondents generally consider internal audit to be conducted responsibly and yield valuable outcomes.

The mean scores reveal how respondents perceive the various facets of internal audit, from objective achievement to the quality of audit findings and recommendations. An especially noteworthy finding for assessing the clarity and logical presentation of internal audit reports, suggesting that respondents find these reports well-structured and easy to comprehend. This indicates that internal audit is seen as an effective and transparent process that contributes positively to the organization's goals.

The results contradict a study conducted on unlisted SMEs in China, which highlighted the overall inadequacy in assessing internal audit work. Furthermore, the study's descriptive analysis suggests that when SMEs have effective internal audits, the internal auditors' abilities are relatively lacking, while their communication and collaboration with external auditors is notably strong. It appears that enterprises prioritize strengthening ties with external auditors rather than enhancing the skills of their internal auditors (Lihuan, 2022).

The Level of Business Performance of the SMEs in terms of Financial Performance

In Table 3.1, the first item states that the profit increased annually has the highest mean of 4.10 which is interpreted as high. The second item has the next highest mean, stating that the number of the company's assets increased. The fourth item, indicating an increase in sales growth, has the lowest mean of 3.67 but is still interpreted as high. The SMEs' level of business performance in the financial aspect has an overall mean of 3.83 and is interpreted as high.

This trend in consistently positive financial indicators not only suggests that SMEs are achieving commendable financial outcomes but also signifies a trajectory toward sustained growth and stability. Their consistent positive performance across various financial metrics lays a strong foundation, positioning SMEs favorably for enduring success amidst the competitive market landscape. Beyond showcasing their resilience, this trend becomes a beacon for potential investors, illustrating SMEs as promising investment opportunities and indicating readiness for forging enduring partnerships. This pattern of success not only fortifies their market presence but also paves the way for collaborative ventures that could propel SMEs further toward long-term prosperity and market leadership.

A related study was conducted to assess the financial performance of Super Auto Forge. The analysis of financial reports indicates that the overall performance is moderately positive. The study highlights that while the business's liquidity and profitability are satisfactory, there is inefficiency in the working capital turnover ratio. The analysis involved examining the business's financial statement, including the balance sheet and profit and loss statement, to pinpoint strengths and weaknesses. The findings suggest a yearly increase in financial performance, yet further efforts are needed for greater effectiveness (Suresh, 2020).

The Level of Business Performance of the SMEs in terms of Non-Financial Performance

In Table 3.2, the item implying employees' trust in leadership has the highest mean of 4.29 which is interpreted as high. Moreover, the item stating that relations with suppliers are quite good and stable got the second highest mean of 4.24 and is interpreted as high. The item describing that the number of customer complaints within the last 12 months has decreased obtained the lowest mean of 3.52 and is still interpreted as high. The SMEs' level of business performance in terms of non-financial performance obtained an overall mean of 4.04 which was interpreted as high.

The non-financial performance aspect shows very positive results for SMEs. They maintain strong relationships with suppliers, involve them actively in research and development, and have high employee satisfaction and retention rates. Their organizational efficiency, employee commitment, and responsiveness to customer complaints are commendable. While there's room for improvement in reducing customer complaints, SMEs excel in addressing them faster than competitors and display better risk-taking behavior compared to their peers.

In Pahang, Malaysia, there is a similar study wherein 200 questionnaires were being handed to micro-enterprises located in the area. The findings reveal that the majority of these selected micro-enterprises demonstrate strong performance, both financially and non-financially. However, their strength lies more prominently in non-financial aspects than in financial ones. The study highlights that many enterprises consider qualitative information crucial for enhancing their performance. As a result, non-financial performance measures are anticipated to serve as primary indicators for future performance assessment (Jamil, & Ahmad, 2020).

Significant Relationship Between the Level of Internal Control and the Level of Business Performance of SMEs

The analysis used the correlation coefficient (r-value) and the associated p-value to determine the strength and significance of this relationship shown in the table. Data shows a p-value of 0.002 with r-value of 0.625. This low p-value indicates that the relationship between internal control and business performance is statistically significant. In other words, it is highly unlikely that this relationship occurred by random chance alone. Based on these findings, the decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) is appropriate. However, in this case, the data strongly suggests that the level of internal control indeed has a significant relationship with the level of business performance in SMEs.

These findings have important implications for SMEs, as they highlight the importance of having robust internal control mechanisms in place. Effective internal controls can enhance various aspects of business performance, including financial stability, risk management, and overall operational efficiency. SMEs should consider investing in strengthening their internal control systems to potentially improve their business performance and competitiveness in the market. Further research and analysis may be warranted to explore the specific aspects of internal control that have the most significant impact on SME performance and to develop practical strategies for implementation.

These results align with a comparable study carried out in China, investigating the connection between internal control measures and the sustainable gain of SMEs. The findings demonstrate that robust internal controls play a significant role in enabling SMEs to attain sustainable growth. Additionally, this impact is influenced by the presence of multiple large shareholders, indicating that the significance of internal control is heightened in SMEs with several significant shareholders (Wang et al., 2019).

Significant Relationship Between the Level of Internal Audit and the Level of Business Performance of the SMEs

The correlation coefficient in this context is 0.355, indicating a positive but relatively weak relationship between internal audit levels and SMEs' business performance. Although a tendency for improvement exists as internal audit levels increase, caution is advised due to the correlation falling below the 0.5 threshold. Additionally, the p-value of 0.114 exceeds the significance level of 0.5, indicating a lack of statistical significance and suggesting that the observed correlation could be due to chance rather than a causal relationship. Based on these statistical results, the researchers do not have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), suggesting that the level of internal audit does not have a significant relationship with the level of business performance level in SMEs.

This suggests that as the internal audit level increases, there is a tendency for business performance to improve. The results imply a weak positive correlation between the level of internal audit and the SMEs' level of company performance. Therefore, SMEs should be cautious when attributing internal audit procedures exclusively for the inadequate business performance. The results highlight the complexity of SME's performance and imply that other aspects, such as market conditions and leadership, might have greater impact. This highlights the need for comprehensive management strategies that consider a wide range of influencing factors to enhance SMEs competitiveness and success. The statistical analysis within the study suggests that the internal audit function can reliably forecast business growth.

The results align with a similar study carried out in Ghana. The study's empirical findings surprisingly indicated that internal audits tended to have adverse effects on the performance of listed enterprises in Ghana. These results contradicted the commonly held belief that the oversight roles performed by internal auditors, focusing on auditing, financial reporting, internal control, and risk management within organizations, would inevitably lead to enhanced performance, safeguarding the interests of shareholders and the public. (Puni & Anlesinya, 2019).

Internal Control and Internal Audit have a Significant Influence on the Business Performance of the SMEs

Table 6 summarizes a regression analysis exploring how internal control and internal audit affect small and medium enterprises' (SMEs) performance. The constant term, starting the table, displays the intercept of the regression equation with a coefficient of 0.400. The variables of interest, "Control" and "Audit," show unstandardized coefficients of 0.761 and 0.088, respectively, highlighting "Control" as having a more substantial positive impact on business performance compared to "Audit." Standardized coefficients (Beta) emphasize "Control" (0.590) as more influential than "Audit" (0.073) in explaining variance in the dependent variable. The statistical significance is evident through "Control" having a significant t-value (2.827, $p = 0.011$), while "Audit" lacks significance ($t = 0.349$, $p = 0.731$). Finally, the overall model, reflected by multiple R (0.628) and F-value (5.872, $p = 0.011$), shows moderate positive correlation and statistical significance.

The findings suggest the importance for SMEs to place a greater emphasis on prioritizing and strengthening their internal control mechanisms as a means to enhance their overall performance. By doing so, SMEs can better navigate the complexities of their business operations, manage risks, and ensure greater financial stability. However, it's essential to keep in mind that this analysis is based on the

data and variables provided, and other factors not included in the model may also influence SMEs' performance.

Ultimately, a business succeeds when it sets up its operations to meet what consumers want. Business performance checks how well a company manages its day-to-day tasks according to its plans. It is about seeing if the company is good at turning its big ideas into actions every day. It measures how well a company makes its strategies work to reach its goals (WallStreetMojo, 2023).

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